

THE IMPORTANCE OF CREATIVE TASKS IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: This article talks about the importance of creative tasks in preschool children's learning of English, and suggests how to improve children's intelligence, quickness, and memorization of new words through the use of various creative games for preschool children.

Key words: Creative games, child, preschool education, intelligence, ingenuity, game, speech, multimedia, didactic games.

Today, large-scale reforms are being implemented in all areas of our country. In particular, fundamental changes are being made in the field of preschool education, the issue of education of preschool children has become an urgent issue at the state level. In this regard, our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's initiatives, decrees and decisions are still being implemented. Therefore, after gaining independence, great attention is being paid to learning foreign languages in our country. For example, on December 10, 2012, "On further improvement of the system of learning foreign languages" This is evidenced by the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the introduction of continuous teaching of foreign languages in the first grades of general education schools starting from the 2013-2014 academic year.¹ Nowadays, not only students of schools, lyceums and higher educational institutions, but also students of preschool educational organizations and employees working in various fields teaching of foreign languages, especially English, has been started. The reason for this is that learning the languages of economically, scientifically and culturally developed countries is the main factor in acquiring the achievements of world science and development. We use various methods and methods to develop children's creative abilities and activities. Indeed, English scholar John Locke expressed the following idea: "The soul of a new baby born into the world."²

Pre-school education is like cotton wool. In his opinion, what to write in the child's soul in the style of "top-clean cotton" is entirely up to the adults. Therefore, how a child develops into a person, i.e. what personal qualities are found in him, depends on the experience he gets from life, life concepts and ideas he gets in the process of communicating with others. It is necessary to pay attention to children and find out their interests with various questions such as quizzes and picture tests. After talking with each child and determining their interests, we should start the lesson with suitable songs, games, interesting and colorful multi-character handouts that attract attention. First of all, we greet the children and before explaining our topic, we should conduct small conversations with children about our topic, listen to their opinions, start with songs and games about our topic. Because it is easy and interesting for children to develop an understanding of the subject and to understand the lesson. We should gradually distribute our interesting handouts, for example: we can ask children about their favorite color or their favorite cartoon characters. After distributing the handouts, we will slowly explain the topic by asking them what they thought when they saw them. We also use cartoons and multimedia to develop children's creative abilities. Cartoons in English are one of the best assistants in teaching English. Children love cartoons and enjoy watching them back to back. Therefore, cartoons in English help to solve many problems of teaching children a foreign language at the same time. Cartoons - while children do not understand

¹ Jalolov J.J. Foreign language teaching methodology.

² Saydaliev S.S. Essays on the methodology of teaching foreign languages

the words in the cartoon during language learning, they try to understand the words they use through the actions of the cartoon characters. This is one of the interesting and effective ways for children to learn the language. We also use fairy tales. During the audio fairy tale, children look at the pictures together with the teacher and at the same time pronounce the words.³

To make listening to English audio fairy tales more interesting, we can use fairy tale drawing as one of the methods of fairy tale therapy. It is necessary to properly explain to children how important it is to learn foreign languages through natural conditions. For example, the great thinker Abu Nasr Farabi knew many foreign languages perfectly, was able to speak them easily and created in them. Such an opportunity motivated scholars to study world science and do great things. Thus, as our grandfather Navoi used to say, we should not forget the idea that "He who knows the language knows what he knows." There are interesting games in the process of teaching English and Russian. We should mention that, in teaching children, it is necessary to use such games in which all students can participate equally and learn new things from the lesson (for example, memorizing new vocabulary, if this process is repeated every day, the student's vocabulary horizons increase to a higher level). It is inappropriate to start the lesson with grammar concepts, especially for younger students, because it causes them to get bored quickly. As a result, the interest in the class may fade. Even the process of greeting with them should be started in an unconventional way, for example, the method of starting the class with an English song about greeting is an effective method when the teacher enters. If the lesson continues in this way, the students will not lose their attention to one task during the lesson. They even look forward to English lessons. We have to use different methods and games so that we don't make the children bored. The purpose of the tennis game is to increase the speed of the students. This game is similar to a chain game and takes place within the chosen theme. In this case, a new word should be added to the last letter of the said word, for example, if the topic name is "Animals", if it starts with the word "Tiger" without deviating from the topic, the second participant should say "rabbit". he continues. Thus the game continues. A student who stops during the game and cannot answer within 5 minutes will be removed from the game and will be continued with the rest of the students. Playing the game with a class, that is, with many people, will be very interesting and enjoyable. This game can also be played by changing the theme. At the same time, in the process of organizing games, connecting them with various technical means also serves to increase interest. Because in today's rapidly developing age, not all young people, teenagers and adults are indifferent to modern technologies. Therefore, it is possible to achieve an effective result by organizing interesting science games on computers.

In short, when using games, we can change them depending on the knowledge and age of children, that is, make them easier or more complicated. The purpose of these above-mentioned games is to strengthen the memory of students, increase their mental capacity, quickness, intelligence, easy memorization of new words, and most importantly, meaningful organization of the lesson. By introducing advanced methods of education with modern pedagogy and information communication, it is desirable to make the growing young generation an expert in the languages they are learning, and on the basis of this, they can speak these languages easily.

REFERENCES

1. Jalolov J.J. Foreign language teaching methodology. T.: Teacher, 2016.

³ Khoshimoe UD., Yakubov I Ya. Methodology of teaching English

2. Saydaliev S.S. Essays on the methodology of teaching foreign languages. Namangan: NamDU, 2018.
3. Khoshimoe UD., Yakubov I Ya. Methodology of teaching English. T.: Sharq, 2017.